

A threshold for collaborative innovation: exploring the dimensions of liminality in a data economy initiative

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Collaborative innovation requires space for different parties to meet, exchange information, engage in dialogue, and eventually create new solutions. Despite the increased scholarly and practical interest, understanding how such spaces are initiated and sustained remains scarce. In this study, we focus on a national data economy initiative to investigate a virtual and mental space where relevant and interested cross-sectoral parties can join, share information and identify shared interests for research and development in the data economy. We investigate the early phases of collaborative innovation through the lens of liminality and show how individuals' sensemaking narratives manifest the different dimensions of liminality. We contribute to the research on collaborative innovation and spaces by theorising liminality in the context of our paper as a three-dimensional concept of confusion–clarity, isolation–communal, and stagnation–movement that creates a threshold for collaborative innovation. Our study offers a more nuanced understanding of the less studied, yet critical, early phase of collaborative innovation, hence contributing to the research and practice of the emergence of collaborative innovation.

1. Introduction

The current era is characterised by an urgency to find solutions to highly complex and systemic problems. One of these issues relates to how digitalisation and abundant data can best serve countries and their citizens. Many countries have tackled these challenges by widely adopting digital technologies and new ways of cross-sectoral co-creation (e.g. de Silva, Lavelle, et al., 2022; de Silva, Schmidt, et al., 2022) and by investing in a robust data economy (DE) (European Commission, 2017). The proliferation of

data and digital technologies indeed provides boundless opportunities to boost growth through efficiency and innovation; however, the complexity of current problems calls for expertise and solutions that cannot be found in silos. Thus, the need for an open and collaborative approach to innovation is immense (Chesbrough, 2003, 2020). Solving complex problems requires complementary actors across sectoral boundaries to jointly generate new ideas and engage in the process of transforming these ideas into new or improved solutions (Baldwin and von Hippel, 2011; Bogers et al., 2017; Yström and Agogué, 2020).

For different parties to meet, exchange information, and engage in dialogue for collaborative innovation, a space is required (Peschl and Fundneider, 2008, 2014; Tsoukas, 2009; Arena et al., 2017; Bessant, 2020; Yström and Agogué, 2020; Ollila and Yström, 2021). Spaces are needed to bring actors together around a common purpose, facilitate collaboration, and support relational engagement (von Hippel, 2005; Enkel et al., 2009; Greer and Lei, 2012; Garud et al., 2013; Heil and Bornemann, 2018) so that parties can make sense (Gioia and Chittipeddi, 1991) and learn together (Beckman and Barry, 2007). Despite the idea of open innovation already being popular in the early 2000s (Chesbrough, 2003) and the subsequent research and practical interest in the topic, we know surprisingly little about what happens before actors engage in collaborative innovation (Garud et al., 2013; Uhl-Bien, 2021) and how space for collaborative innovation can be created. Still, after 20 years of prolific research on interorganisational collaborative innovation, most initiatives never reach their full potential (Viki, 2016; Caccamo, 2020).

This study was motivated by this limited understanding of what happens before the possibility of collaborative innovation. Research on interorganisational collaboration has shown that this phase involves a collaborative exploration process (cf. Attour and Barbaroux, 2016), in which organisations define common goals and explore ways to develop and combine their assets to achieve them. Researchers' focus has been on the organisation and either the actions and strategies through which focal organisations initiate and further control such collaborative initiatives (e.g. Dattée et al., 2018) or the capabilities and knowledge that organisations develop to engage in collaborative innovation effectively (e.g. Swink, 2006). Therefore, individual participants and their roles in (initiating) collaborative innovation are usually neglected. Studies that focus on the individual level are scarce in the management and innovation literature but are by no means absent (e.g. Lowik et al., 2017; Mazzucchelli et al., 2019). For example, Mazzucchelli et al. (2019) showed the crucial role of individual motivation and individual engagement in efficacious and frequent knowledge sharing, a vital aspect of successful collaborative innovation.

To understand more of what kinds of individual-level aspects precede collaborative innovation, we study the initiation of a collaborative innovation space with the lens of *liminality*. Recent literature on spaces for collaborative innovation has highlighted the importance of liminality (or a liminal space) for collaborative innovation since being in that state (and space) allows for the contemplation of

multiple perspectives and cognitive exchange among diverse actors (Caccamo, 2020). Liminality refers to the experience of being in a transitional state, being on the boundary between one state but not quite being into the next and holding in intense periods of development and learning (e.g. Czarniawska and Mazza, 2003; Tempest and Starkey, 2004; Ryan, 2019). In the midst of complexity and constant change, these positions of ambiguity and uncertainty (Ellis and Ybema, 2010; Beech, 2011) can be characterised as conditions of being 'betwixt and between' or of being at the limits of existing structures (Tempest and Starkey, 2004). Nevertheless, there is still much to understand about what being in this liminal state entails and how individuals make sense of it.

Our research questions were as follows: *What is the threshold for creating space for collaborative innovation, and how does liminality as a lens help us make sense of this threshold?* By answering these questions, our study also answers Yström and Agogué's (2020) recent call for a further understanding of the microfoundations and the meaning of what individuals do to initiate a space for collaborative innovation.

We particularly focus on the early phases of a national DE initiative to create a space called the 'Data Economy Boardroom' (DEB), where all relevant and interested parties from a variety of sectors in Finland can join, share information and identify shared interests. Studying the initiation of collaborative innovation space through the lens of liminality, we show how individuals' sensemaking narratives manifest different dimensions of liminality (i.e. confusion–clarity, isolation–communal, and stagnation–movement) and their motivations for collaborative innovation. In adopting this perspective, we perceive liminal not only as a physical or virtual transitioning space (Stephenson et al., 2020) and a place of innovation (cf. Caccamo, 2020), but also as an individual's mental state being on the precipice or threshold of something new but not being quite there yet (e.g. Ollila and Yström, 2020).

We next discuss space and liminality in the context of collaborative innovation, introduce our methodology, and present our exploration of being at the threshold of collaborative innovation.

2. Theoretical background

2.1. On space in collaborative innovation

Fast technological changes and related complexities have made it difficult to innovate alone successfully. Firms increasingly collaborate to

leverage complementary knowledge and resources, as well as share risks in global competition based on continuous innovation. However, interorganisational collaboration for innovation is a complex and challenging endeavour (Dhanaraj and Parkhe, 2006), where diverse parties must build a shared understanding, reach a common goal, and design the structures and processes to govern their collaboration (Ring and Van de Ven, 1994). It is by no means easy, and research on interorganisational collaboration shows that partners often do not reach their goals. In addition, initiating such a collaboration can be challenging, and many early endeavours may fail even before they start (Doz et al., 2000; Välikangas and Jarvenpaa, 2021). Collaborative innovation has been defined as ‘the creation of innovations across firm boundaries through the sharing of ideas, knowledge, expertise, and opportunities’ (Miles et al., 2005; Ketchen et al., 2007, p. 371).

Different collaborative innovation spaces (Yström and Agogué, 2020; Ollila and Yström, 2021) can facilitate multi-actor collaboration by bringing together public and private actors (e.g. von Hippel, 2005; Enkel et al., 2009; Heil and Bornemann, 2018) with relevant innovation assets (Sørensen and Torfing, 2012). These spaces are needed for participants to meet, exchange information and engage in dialogue (Tsoukas, 2009; Arena et al., 2017; Bessant, 2020) around a common purpose (Ring and Van de Ven, 1994; von Hippel, 2005) to learn and build a shared understanding.

The more complex the innovation and related context (with diverse actors, systemic technologies, and their interdependencies), the more important the time and space available for making sense of the situation to enable both individual and collective learning (Beckman and Barry, 2007) and to create a mutual understanding (Brown and Duguid, 1991; Wenger, 1998). Without a common purpose and space, collaborative innovation may fail or never come to be (Miles et al., 2000; Adner, 2012; Di Fiore and Vetter, 2016; Viki, 2016; Caccamo, 2020). Furthermore, initiating and maintaining collaborative innovation with actors’ diverse priorities and worldviews is a difficult task, not to mention the challenges in sustaining engagement to prevent its premature termination (Bartel and Garud, 2009; Ferraro et al., 2015). Current research on collaborative innovation and spaces acknowledges these challenges; however, it provides a scarce understanding of the role of space in the initiation and emergence of collaborative innovation. We use this as a starting point in investigating how cross-sectoral actors

come together and how they perceive space and its purpose.

Traditionally, organisational spaces are viewed as fixed, physical workspaces or virtual, transitioning spaces (Stephenson et al., 2020). Recently, Capdevila (2017) introduced localised communities as representing common cognitive spaces where members with a common interest can interact and work together to develop innovations for their own use. Caccamo (2020) also referred to such spaces as liminal spaces that allow for multiple perspectives and cognitive exchange.

2.2. Liminality in collaborative innovation

Liminality is an experience, a condition, or a temporal state of being that is characterised by being on the precipice or threshold of something new but not being quite there yet, while holding in intense periods of development and learning (e.g. Czarniawska and Mazza, 2003; Tempest and Starkey, 2004; Ryan, 2019). Coined by van Gennep (1909) and further developed by Turner (1969), liminality has gained increasing attention in organisation research during recent years through the acknowledgement of various transitional and transient states in people’s working lives (e.g. Garsten, 1999; Küpers, 2011; Ibarra and Obodaru, 2016; Tagliaventi, 2019).

In the organisational literature, liminality has often been referred to as the condition of being betwixt and between or of existing at the limits of existing structures (Tempest and Starkey, 2004), characterising individuals’ positions of ambiguity and uncertainty (Beech, 2011). For example, the in-between or liminal positions of people embedded in interorganisational networks present a particular challenge for the enactment of identity (see, e.g. Ellis and Ybema, 2010).

In organisational contexts, these temporal liminal spaces inhabited by people have been discussed mostly as physical (Shortt, 2015; Söderlund and Borg, 2018), for example, open labs and maker spaces, but also as emotional (e.g. Muhr et al., 2019), or metaphorical (e.g. Czarniawska and Mazza, 2003), capturing a more complex image of the condition at hand. Usually, the application of the liminality metaphor emphasises ‘the changeful nature of [the] subjects, the multiple meanings that can co-exist and the negative psychological consequences of extended liminality’ (Beech, 2011, p. 287). The literature discussing collaborative innovation spaces views these spaces as being in-between organisations (Ollila and Yström, 2020), or otherwise liminal in nature, and actors’ experiences related to these spaces as being not here

nor there or being nowhere, or as specific zones of ‘third places’ (Oldenburg, 1989) on neutral territories. According to Söderlund and Borg (2018), liminal spaces emerge when people come together to share temporary spaces and learn about their various roles, either within or outside a formal organisation. In such third places, traditional routines and norms do not constrain unfolding activities in a similar way as in normal daily life (Oldenburg, 1989), and actors may suspend or renegotiate (Söderlund and Borg, 2018) their professional roles and activities. This provides possibilities to perceive and experience things in a liminal space differently and thus create new combinations and creative solutions that enhance collaborative innovation.

Building on these recent developments, we conceptualise *the liminal space not only as a physical or virtual transitioning space and place of innovation but as individuals’ being on the precipice or threshold of something new but not being quite there yet, while holding in intense periods of development and learning*. This threshold for collaborative innovation is therefore an abstract and mental state, a psychological, liminal experience (Stenner, 2017) of being part of the sensemaking process with other actors with whom one can learn and develop something new.

Our interest lies in individual participants’ narratives of the *meaning* of what they do to initiate and shape a collaborative space and through these narratives, we explore the different dimensions of liminality. We next explain our methodological choices.

3. Methodology

This study is an interpretative narrative inquiry (Boje, 2001) to explore and develop an in-depth understanding of the conditions of being at the *threshold* of collaborative innovation.

Our approach allows us to gain a richer understanding of *what the threshold is for creating space for collaborative innovation*, and moreover, *how liminality as a lens helps us make sense of this threshold* from a particular standpoint in time (Bruner, 1991; Weick et al., 2005), capturing ‘*movement from past to present to future woven together in a meaningful sequence*’ (Fachin and Langley, 2018, p. 314). Furthermore, our narrative inquiry refers to both the methods used for data collection and analysis (see Sections 3.2 and 3.3), in which a narrative serves as the primary form by which human experience is made meaningful (Brown et al., 2008). First, in relation to narrative data collection, our interest was to

explore what and how the core group of individuals taking part in launching the DEB would narrate the initiative without a structured interview agenda but instead using a loose guide for a conversation (Connelly and Clandinin, 1990; Riessman, 1993; see our Appendix A). Second, the narratives served as an analytical clue to search for answers to the overarching question of ‘what is the story’ (Weick et al., 2005), which they have become part of. Our narrative inquiry allowed us to remain attentive to how informants narrated their projections and anticipations of the future (*cf.* Stigliani and Ravasi, 2012). Finally, narratives shed light on individuals’ experiences (e.g. Ryan, 2019) and common purpose (Ring and Van de Ven, 1994; von Hippel, 2005) of a liminal space from various perspectives, providing a nuanced understanding of the emergence of collaborative innovation.

3.1. Empirical and temporal settings

The story of this study takes place in Finland. During the 2019 Presidency of the Council of the EU, Finland placed the growth of the DE high on the European agenda. According to recent reports from the Ministry of Transport and Communications (2021), Finland has been well involved in a wide range of initiatives around Europe to develop the DE, including building data spaces, data ecosystems, and big EU projects. When we discuss DE in this study, we refer to an ecosystem of diverse actors, including manufacturers, researchers, and infrastructure providers, that must collaborate to ensure data accessibility and usability (European Commission, 2017; Schmidhuber et al., 2019; Enkel et al., 2020). An ultimate goal of the DE is to enable these actors to create or extract value from this data, which will eventually allow the development of solutions with great potential to solve the complex challenges that human societies are facing today (*Ibid*). Finland has been a strong advocate of the DE; however, the transition has been slowed by a ‘*siloed understanding of the DE, barriers to data sharing, skills gaps, and attitudes*’ (Sitra, 2022). At the time this study began, at the end of 2020, the DE actors worked sectorally in a siloed way that did not serve the need for knowledge sharing to build a shared understanding of the field. The key informants in our study decided to act (further elaboration in the next section).

3.2. Data collection

Our data were collected from a group of individuals initially launching a national, informal experimental initiative, later branded the Data Economy

Boardroom (DEB), organised through a series of virtual events that offered time and space for sharing information and making sense of the state of the DE in the country. This core group represents various industries, such as banking, IT, and digital security, as well as public sector organisations, such as ministries, higher education organisations, and a national think tank.

In October 2020, the third author of the present paper received a phone call from an individual who later became a key informant for the study, I-1, to discuss how to organise the aforementioned DEB space. Their paths crossed during an experiment of bringing experts together from different fields and organisations to prevent Finland's paralysis during COVID-19 challenges (de Silva, Lavelle, et al., 2022; de Silva, Schmidt, et al., 2022). The experiment of fast-paced online collaboration turned out to be an effective way to connect people remotely and rapidly across sectoral borders. This sparked the desire to see something similar happen in another cross-sectoral context taking effect in Finland – the DE. The authors realised that the DEB offered a unique opportunity and unusual research access to study the very early phases of collaborative innovation. This uniqueness arises from the difficulty of identifying initiatives that are about to emerge, making this case revelatory (Eisenhardt and Graebner, 2007).

The launching phase of the DEB was a set of three virtual events aimed at creating space and time for collective sensemaking and learning. By constructing a real-time view of the activities in ongoing projects and plans across sectors, the overall aim was to 'go in the same direction together with others', as worded by one of our key informants, to unleash the potential of DE. The DEB events were open to all, and invitations to events were distributed by the core group. The first DEB event gathered 66 attendees, and the two following events had over 100 attendees each. The interests of various actors were seen as proof of the need to bring people together to share information and make sense of the DE in a collective fashion.

During the initiative, the first author attended several planning meetings and conversed informally with I-1, gaining a richer understanding of the context of the researched individuals in action (Shotter, 2006). The first author interviewed 11 individuals from November 2020 to early January 2021. Based on a research collaboration discussion with I-1 taking action, the other 10 key persons invited to take part in the research were selected, as they were actively taking part in the initiative across sectors. See Table 1 for the list of informants.

Initially, the aim was to learn about the initiation process and how it was perceived by the key informants who attended the kick-off meeting on October 20, 2020 and were involved in planning and executing the first DEB events in November and December. A description of the data is available in Appendix B.

3.3. Data analysis

Our analytical approach applied a thematic model of narrative analysis (Riessman, 1993; Esin, 2011), which further facilitated the comparative analysis of the research participants' different descriptions of the phenomenon under study. Furthermore, our analytical process resembles the categorical-content analysis approach by Lieblich et al. (1998), which focused on the thematic similarities and differences between narrative accounts in interviews. This means that we sought connections across narrative segments/elements and further the themes both within and between the accounts given by the participants.

The preliminary analysis process began alongside the first interviews. The interviewer (first author) rewrote the handwritten interview memos into Word documents immediately following each interview to summarise the main points of the conversations. After 8 out of 11 interviews had been transcribed verbatim, the interviewer provided the core group by December 18, 2020, with a descriptive summary of the interviewees' main viewpoints, the purpose and expectations for the DEB, and its principal activities to support networking and learning (see Appendix C for the Table of Contents). This initial step in our analysis revealed the similarities and diversities of the research participants' views over the purpose of DEB and personal motivation to take part in the initiative (further analysed as informants' parallel narratives; see Table 2). We interpreted these as relevant aspects of the empirical phenomenon and thus as promising themes for further analysis and theorising (cf. Sinkovics and Alfoldi, 2012).

When we further extracted interview accounts of personal descriptions of what DEB was and how and why individuals were engaged with the initiative, the interviewees' expressions of emotions, values and anticipations (Gioia and Chittipeddi, 1991; Ring and Van de Ven, 1994; Stigliani and Ravasi, 2012) were given attention since they were assumed to convey the personally meaningful reasons for taking part in the initiative. Through analysis of the interviews, it became apparent that our informants perceived the basic activities of what was happening and what should happen in the short term in the DEB space differently, that is observing and creating a shared understanding of what others were doing and what

Table 1. The list of the informants

Informant	Description of the informant	Age	Main area of business	Years in the data economy industry or similar	Date of interview	Length of interview (min)
I-1	Navigating into the 'unknown' of data economy; building better understanding and collective wisdom	61–65	Public financial administration	30	1.12.2020	29:55
I-2	Pioneer in digitalisation in the country, an inspiring activist and dynamo in the background having a strong own vision, drive, and motivation for the data economy	71–75	Banking / Senior Activism	Decades	23.11.2020	32:30
I-3	Spanning boundaries of the private and public sectors to enable systemic phenomena, pursuing common understanding	46–50	Lobbying	5	24.11.2020	38:24
I-4	Holding a multiperspective and critical view of substances of the data economy development	51–55	Higher education and start-up business	20	27.11.2020	24:25
I-5	Sensing atmosphere, having a personal passion for data economy developments and opportunities within	35–40	Public administration	1	27.11.2020	27:06
I-6	Building relationships and networks by connecting the who and what, advocating co-operation in data economy by profession	35–40	National think tank	4	30.11.2020	33:22
I-7	Learning to know the grass root actors of the data economy	41–45	Public administration	7	2.12.2020	31:09
I-8	Mapping and documenting the process of the initiative; enabling and creating conceptual ladders between data economy actors on a concrete level of action	46–50	Facilitation	–	3.12.2020	35:38
I-9	Working with and for competitors' cooperation; seeing initial cooperation as creating a starting point of doing and solving things better together	51–55	Banking	25	18.12.2020	32:00
I-10	To make ecosystem building legitimate with the power of a large group of people and to create equal competition	46–50	Digital business	20	4.1.2021	38:57
I-11	Calling for fast investments in infrastructure and an increase of intellectual capital as a form of competitive advantage	35–40	Digital security and business	15	8.1.2021	26:26

Table 2. Parallel narratives, thematic categories, and representative empirical material

The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Representative empirical material
<p>I-1 was initiating the Boardroom to increase and build an understanding of the data economy phenomenon and 'explore different directions' collectively. This would simultaneously alleviate the lack of I-1's own knowledge and let I-1 follow-up and take part in the interesting developments in the data economy. For I-1 the core idea was to agree on a 'big picture' with other players in the field while still challenging the current state and creating alternative ways of doing things. I-1 emphasised that 'getting out of silos' and learning from the conversations, were at the heart of generating ideas and possibly innovations from the Boardroom</p>	<p>Confusion–clarity Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement</p> <p><i>'To better understand different actors' doings to go in the same direction together and to identify central goals for the country, create a shared understanding and get new action in the move'. – 'There may be curious, solution-focused people who focus on finding strategies, projects, or innovations together towards the future, while others depending on their role might be worried, sorrowful, or even feel guilty if there is a lack of understanding of the next steps. It may be due to the financial or political or any other pressures in the situation'. – 'Lack of knowledge. There is so much information and facts that it is difficult to follow what is relevant to your own doings. Interest or motivation to understand the interdependencies and connections to others' doings and how the data economy works then. – It would be inspiring to get a grasp on what the main agenda for [our country] could be and not to act alone in our own small silo: how [our country] is going to keep up with things, how we can sustain our well-being, how our taxation will function in the future, how the firms will manage here'. – 'Ought to draw and discuss the big picture, whether all agree to head toward that direction. And to agree what is the level of issues selected to be discussed that benefit the whole [country] or should the EU-level issues have their own thematic discussion group? – Ought to learn from research and model the product development area, ought to observe and foresee the prospects. Should have a curious mindset and challenge the present modes of action in a positive way for finding alternative ways of doing things'. – 'Get out from silos' – 'Experimenting and finding new relationships in networks could arise new discussions, ideas, and even innovations. Ideas of certain kinds of ecosystems to be formed could be born, too. In the world of interdependencies, we should understand this whole before solving out single problems or needs'. – 'I have learned from each conversation and others have learned something else. There are always new ideas when people from different sectors are collected together'. – There are three levels for national competitive advantage: international and EU-level matters, EU data strategy, and EU-level programs to actively attend. What kind of influence [our country] should have in the EU, as here we have more understanding of data economy than in many other countries, if considered, how to act compared to [world's largest economies]. It is long known that Europe should choose its own way with the MyData approach to ensure people are able to control their own data. And to understand what the needed building blocks are for this: who is doing and having the control of them and whether it is the responsibility of the public sector or competing markets with many different programs, how these common blocks can benefit all'</i></p>

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
<p>I-7 was in the core team to learn about the Boardroom concept. I-7's interest was to get a grasp of the grassroots-level activities in the data economy and be part of building a forum as a starting point to have a common understanding and for 'knowledge transfer'. Building this forum would also bring structure for meeting people. The initiative would also support their work at the ministry and alleviate the 'loneliness' of the work of a public officer. I-7 also hoped that they could be building a 'joint message' to the EU-level discussions and make an impact together</p>	<p>Confusion–clarity Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement</p>	<p>'And we can learn something about this forum concept and how things are done, so in that sense, we have some kind of selfish purpose also'. – 'There is so much development happening in companies, at the national level and in legislation and there are so many different levels in development, so this kind of forum serves well as a faster forum for knowledge transfer. – [W]e are lawmakers and maybe not always involved with grassroots level – [W]e try to soak up information about what is happening in the field' – 'It is a great wealth that we have this kind of cooperation and informal discussion club in [our country], there is no such thing in Europe according to my understanding, especially in a field with a fast tempo like this. It is a good starting point that we build this kind of common understanding, and that we understand each other and have this kind of interaction over borders. It is a good asset (towards Europe)'. – 'Having this kind of structure for a forum makes it easy to have conversations, listen, and join in – maybe it inspires to see enthusiastic people taking part and doing lots of things benefiting us all so that supports my own work, too'. – 'Often the work feels quite hard and a bit lonely especially in times of Covid, so it is good to share what is happening with others'. – 'When we share our opinions in the European Union, our message becomes a joint message on a national level – in these kinds of discussion forums we are able to hear the opinions of others and the needs from the field and share the problems we see in administration'. 'We've been able to get our messages of human-centered data economy to Europe and that ethics is a very important aspect in data economy development. So, the more we have these kinds of messages, the more impact we can have for the development of European data economy legislation'</p>	
<p>I-4 was there to follow up on the developments in the field of data economy. I-4 saw it important to link different sectors with the Boardroom, and through it enable knowledge sharing and coordination of common initiatives. It would be important to create a tight network for collaboration, where it was possible to raise debates and think critically, and gain as many views as possible. I-4 saw the momentum to make an impact in the EU data strategy</p>	<p>Confusion–clarity Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement</p>	<p>'It would be important to create a national vision of programs that we like to profile with and to have visibility. – Are we going to have a common understanding due to consensus or are we going to use some tools to work on our shared view of the situation?' – 'Hopefully this also raises debates that challenge this whole development every now then and, and perhaps it raises even critical tones of voices of the direction we are taking. A kind of open discussion and not only smiling talk. – [S]haring knowledge about 'beginnings', looking for more open common 'beginnings' and who is taking charge and how to join those'. – 'How education could be linked better to this Boardroom and its activities?' – 'A good possibility for companies, not only to network but to collaborate in a tight network' – 'Our chance to impact EU data strategy is bigger than the size of our country, it is important to have input and lead and understand European developmental paths'. – 'I have been taking part in these initiatives through my work roles for quite a time. Now it is momentum to an impact, and it is a very interesting phase to closely follow what our national position and European impact on the global data economy could be. It is a challenging and motivating theme'</p>	

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
I-3 I-3 wanted to see a common understanding of the most important programmes in [the country] and in the EU and raise the productivity for the public sector and competitive advantage for companies. To bridge the gap between 'strategic talk' and operationalisation. The work would require them to 'grasp' the systemic phenomenon (of data economy) and to work closely at the interfaces between public, private, and other sectors. I-3 needed to find I-3's own role in the developments and entry to the discussion. Having a digital platform for future discussions would aid the continuation of all this	Confusion–clarity Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement	'Aims to be a grass-root level solution to have a common understanding of all that is going on and what would be important programs to advance over sectoral borders.' – 'How to advance development over sectoral borders and silos in programs'. – 'A very problematic field – siloed sectoral working does not offer the overall view for advancing and managing digitization and data economy, structures are missing' – 'What is our model, how do we understand critical programs for productivity and capabilities in a short and a long term?'. – 'The interface between political, strategic, and operational level talk has quite a gap of what is needed in companies for real and that is what makes it motivating to see'. – '[T]hinking about the interface for the public sector and decision makers and how I could be of service and what I should be doing, so yes there are many angles of entry making this all so interesting'. – '...a (digital) platform to continue discussions, someone needed to facilitate and crystallise discussions'. – 'When we have the next government, everyone knows what information policy is and how to advance transition towards the data economy'	
I-5 I-5 was passionate about being involved with important developments – both the Boardroom and the data economy in general – and advancing the cooperation as networks, or even as ecosystem terms. I-5 stressed that people could join with several points of view, no matter one's title or background organisation	Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement	'One goal is to increase awareness of people in different areas of data economy, new, multidisciplinary phenomena. A larger goal is to build an ecosystem for data economy actors'. – 'We are able to build authentic discussion between public-private and researchers to bring up burning issues, challenges, fears, possibilities'. – 'There are possibilities for cooperation, many timely issues and themes can be brought up as this is a big phenomenon that has to be built bit by bit ... to bring people together and build networks or ecosystems ... when people encounter, ideas and innovations emerge'. – 'The modern business thinking should evolve to networks and economies, a single company cannot act alone anymore, business is not only transactions but there is a lot of co-creation and value creation for markets together'. – 'We must be able to act in ecosystems, there are many programs and different roles to take in the data economy to advance the same goals from different viewpoints'. – 'National infrastructure and capabilities are good and we are forerunners in digitalisation, but these possibilities are not fully utilised in business solutions'. – 'to be an active network member you do not need any title or status, but if you are enthusiastic and passionate about the subject, you are certainly able to get things done and raise debates, raise themes, and activate people. – like I said this is somehow a matter of passion that I see this data economy as an important possibility for [our country] and companies here'	

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
I-6	I-6 stressed the importance of network ties and private-public partnerships. A forum where people would link up like this was currently missing. I-6 was a believer in the 'power of the networks' and was hoping that the Boardroom would let people find solutions to challenges together. A mode of strong collaboration would help take advantage of the country and European-level initiatives and projects	Confusion—clarity Isolation—communal Stagnation—movement	'There is a lot going on around the data economy now. For this reason, it is hard to form an image of the current moment, a picture of what is going on . Therefore, there is a threat that people keep doing their thing in silos and we are not able to take advantage of the best of synergy'. — 'I see this onion-like structure which has these different consortiums on the inner ring, projects wanting to cooperate on a concrete level. — on the outermost ring are the actors who wish to stay updated with and particularly maintain the Boardroom view of different situations in [our country] and in Europe. Probably when something interesting comes and they can embrace it, they will move toward the inner ring to find networks with other actors who are interested in the same subject. — very different goals and perhaps these three Boardroom events have acted out well on the outermost ring, especially in the second event that gathered yet a bigger group of people'. — 'I talk on behalf of strong collaboration , and I believe in the power of these networks'. — '...hope to be able to work together and find shared challenges, where we could join our forces and develop different solutions together'. — 'With this forum, people could better find each other and begin to concretely work together also — At its best, for example, Finnish companies could take advantage of these European initiatives and projects better than before. — for example, this 'recovery money', how are we able to guide it to our companies and projects working with digitalization?'
I-10	I-10 wanted to take part in something innovative that would improve people's lives through technological innovations. By building a network from the Boardroom initiative, they could start improving the country's collective human capital in the data economy field as well as create an equal competitive environment. For I-10, to bring people together as a 'crowd' was to have legitimacy and the possibility to make collective national-level statements regarding the politics of the data economy	Isolation—communal Stagnation—movement	'... everyone is doing their own thing , not enough collaboration. And then, if we are developing solutions, everyone is developing their own solutions but not contributing to a kind of shared human capital' — 'broadly, building this kind of national digital data confirmation network '. — 'securing the competitive advantage of the data economy, with joined forces we can compete in a Nordic way. We share prosperity more or less equally to all'. — 'pretty informal aim at this point, one cannot ask for the attendees to deliver in relation to specific topics. In my opinion, it's more or less voluntary sharing of information and this kind of search for synergies and collaboration '. — '...advancing concrete joint projects'. — '...infrastructure innovations, it begins with them having a sort of seismic impact on society '. — ' more and more people would come and join this Boardroom so that there would be this kind of legitimacy to it . Those issues are being dealt with there'. — '[first] it does not necessarily lead to anything else but acts as an information channel . If we think about where it could lead in the long run, it could give statements and have a more formal role that way. This is naturally more broadly related with politics of data economy.'

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
I-11 I-11 wanted to have a shared responsibility over the data economy developments and national level coordination of infrastructure enabling data economy; faster investments from the government to develop infrastructure and the intellectual capital. I-11 aimed at having a bird's eye view and anticipating new financing and legal regulations needed, due to the nature of collaboration penetrating all sectors. I-11 wished to develop a national competitive advantage from different angles through digitalisation	Isolation—communal Stagnation—movement	'...in many experiments, we have concluded that this kind of national, or cross-sectoral infrastructure is needed to enable the country's data economy'. — 'We have lacked national level coordination in co-developing a national infrastructure and data economy '. — 'We are constantly falling behind in competitiveness in the international market' — 'To find that somebody, a coordinating entity, who would oversee the private and third sector digitalization too, not only the public sector. And then we could find those largest organisations in the private sector, who are now benefiting from the data economy, and who have the R&D and investment capabilities'. — 'And perhaps it crystallises to one bigger single fact that we do not have the ownership of the whole digitalisation scene , no one is ready to make big investments from their own budget for this common digitalisation because it is nobody's responsibility at the moment directly'. — 'we are thinking that when these national level decisions are made, they are not only about the digitalization of public administration services but about the digitalization of the whole country's ecosystem, including the private and the third sector. And that is when we need possibly a bit different kinds of financing models and legal regulations also, and overall, different kinds of thinking of how these solutions should be built'. — 'to analyse those open issues at a concrete level, so that we would have the problems and the entities already working around those problems identified, or who is responsible for starting to solve those problems. And then, someone would take the coordination responsibility over that to some extent. Somebody would be assigned to have genuine ownership of it, both on the public and private sector sides. And we would prepare for the needed development investments, resources and money, and some sort of concrete schedule '. — 'what I miss the most is to have a more shared responsibility to build the infrastructure together with the public and private sector'. — 'If the foundation of our digitalization is not functioning effectively, foreign experts are not interested in us or investments of new companies, which are needed to export our technology and innovations'	

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
I-2 I-2 wanted to continue I-2's 'life's work' and build on the extensive groundwork; to build the infrastructure and rules for the existing and upcoming national-level initiatives. I-2 was the 'dynamic' for the Boardroom pilot, with an aim to create a 'living map' of ongoing projects which would help to sustain and refine the national level objective of data economy collectively and enable making new projects	Confusion-clarity Isolation-communal Stagnation-movement	'It is that universal thing for everybody, we have a burning need to make all projects become aware of what is coming at them'. – 'So that there is understanding, the whole is completely logical after all, it is the big picture, not even difficult to understand. The mission of the Boardroom is to build faith in the future, and it is not expensive anyhow and not unrealistic but quite on the contrary, it uses open national standards that exist already'. – 'there are so many projects, and they do not know of each other at all' – 'to see all that is going on and support each other, their compatibility and collaboration across [organisations]'. And of course, take the digitalisation forward faster in practice'. – ... '[these national level projects] need the infrastructure, and that infrastructure is why we need the Boardroom. ...eco-systems need rulebooks – we need to help these ecosystems to create rulebooks for themselves, and for this, we do have a lot of experience. So that they can get as many commercial actors as possible to create services for people's life situations and for automation...'. – 'this challenge has great importance to us as our actual goal is the platform, which is a shared not-for-profit – the public-private network for confirmed data'. – 'a living map of projects is born, which is then maintained. A list of solutions for general use, called Insight Bank, where one can put new insights and what my initiative offers others, what do I want: trade, skills, and knowhow, linking up with someone, developing tools, and this way would sustain and refine this national objective'	

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
I-9 wanted to have a forum where different projects and initiatives around the data economy could find each other and work together. I-9 aimed at building a mutually beneficial infrastructure and a co-opetition setting development. I-9 trusted success with combining many programs together based on recent good experience and knowledge of that	Confusion–clarity Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement	Representative empirical material	
			<p><i>'The problem is that in a country of this size there are many things happening around this digitalisation nowadays and even with a faster pace, the country has certain demands to achieve some targets and there are many kinds of programs on a private site and then all this stuff between'</i> – <i>'...there are quite many matters others should be aware of not to do the same thing twice, and this higher-level knowledge transfer some programs is what has been missing'</i> – <i>'...And then the question of whether something else needs to happen, I do not know, because this is a kind of forum where these different projects and initiatives should find each other for those parts that benefit the projects and initiatives themselves the most'</i> – <i>'...as in this matter of digital identity, there is a good consensus already, it cannot resolve any other way except by doing it together'</i> – <i>'when making this kind of new digital infrastructure – it must be made as this kind of public private collaboration and a little bit as volunteer based, so that we are involved because we have understood that when we make these common things done together, then we are able to get back to this normal more competitive business with a lot more efficacy. This is the whole story of the Boardroom that we try to get both governmental and private, also co-operative actors invited to the same forum, which is quite uncommon as normally competitors do not participate in the same forum to think about how we could make things better together'</i> – <i>'To make this kind of a new digital infrastructure to notably intensify all kinds of activities in this country must be done like this as a public-private collaboration on a voluntary basis'</i> – <i>'I mean, it is good to be part of this, and we have to be. This [consortium] may connect to quite a many other things as well, and through this, it finds other entities with whom it is worth to investigate things further'</i> – <i>'One start-up had this idea of trying to build this new solution together with a block chain technology... to build a team around a common problem to see if the problem gets solved in that way, rather than waiting – so we have a quite strong proof from near history that it is worth experimenting and we have all the knowledge to do that, which creates a good spirit for motivation - a thought of acting in new ways is credible because it is proved to work'</i></p>

Table 2 (Continued)

The DEB purpose and personal motivations for creating space for collaborative innovation		The three dimensions of liminality	
Informants' parallel narratives	Thematic categories	Representative empirical material	
I-8 wanted to understand and learn, having the curiosity to see how the data-based business will develop and if it will be noticed outside our borders. I-8 provided a digital interface for doing memos of the initiating process that enabled continuation where collective sensemaking became visible. I-8 wanted to make good groundwork and find the added value of getting out of silos	Confusion–clarity Isolation–communal Stagnation–movement	Representative empirical material	
			'...this kind of decision making based on data is one of my own interests, and for example, evaluation of its impact, based on what kind of data is used' – '...curiosity to understand more, to learn' – 'curiosity and interest, like dang, what will come out of this, and what is that something? Is it that new business based on data is building up from the country; will it be visible to the EU or to the world?' – 'so that participants are producing knowledge themselves and a map is drawn or designed according to that' – 'to somehow create added value, to get out of silos, to do something concrete together' – 'when I was doing the kind of concrete things I knew how to, like, when these network members would come into this digital platform, they would see my handwork. The things I had chosen and done' – '...this is a sort of groundwork that might bear fruit in a couple of months' – '...all that data gathered e.g., in textual format and summarised with AI and enabling sharing and participating, I think that whatever networks or smaller groups or how they will evolve, the platform will be useful, and the features will be in a better use in the action than maybe now at the moment when it is more like sharing information'

was going on in the field, having a place for discussion, networking with other DE actors, exploring ideas and knowledge across sectors, sharing knowledge and/or information and learning from others. For some, it was merely a place for connecting and discussing across sectoral borders. However, our interpretation of other accounts reflected a common purpose of how DEB as a space enabled new collaborative initiatives and action beyond the DEB itself in the long term towards, for example, stronger competitive advantages and EU-level impacts through finding means of activating DE actors, exploring and co-creating new ways of doing things, enabling co-competition in the field and critically assessing developments in the DE.

At this time, the analysis progressed deeper, from a descriptive level down through several rounds of dialogue between the first and second authors (between February and April 2021). Through the dialogue, we extracted three different meanings for the collaborative space: understanding, making connections, and taking action. These meanings were derived from the complete set of narrative accounts that reflected the individuals' why and how they were taking part in the initiative. After creating and dividing the pool of accounts into these three meanings for the initiative, we realised that our findings showed how the individuals *mentally entered and inhabited a threshold* for creating space for collaborative innovation from these three vantage points.

During this time, the third and fourth authors engaged with the analysis by providing a fresh set of eyes (Stake, 2008) to further refine the precision and clarity of our findings, as we sought to identify more nuances in the patterns, that is the meanings constructed within and between the separate interviews. At this stage, we searched the literature again for insights (e.g. concepts) that could help us make further sense of our initial findings. As we dug deeper into organisation literature on liminality and its notion of conditions or temporal states of being on the *threshold* of something new but not quite being there yet, holding in intense periods of development and learning (e.g. Tempest and Starkey, 2004), liminality best described our findings and thus could help us further refine our analysis and findings. At this point, our observations of the data, together with the discussions of the DEB initiative with the whole research team, made us question the static description of the three previously constructed meanings for the collaborative space. We realised that to better understand the *threshold*, we needed to shift our attention to how the informants described the state of the DE and how the DEB initiative was the vehicle for navigating that ambiguous and complex environment.

With our refreshed understanding of the DEB initiative, it made more sense to conceptualise and elaborate on the three meanings (understanding, making connections, taking action) based on their state of in-betweenness (or liminality) when creating space for collaborative innovation. Integrating our understanding of the initial meanings of the DEB and notions of being at the *threshold* helped us conceptualise the liminal dimensions of *confusion–clarity*, *isolation–communal*, and *stagnation–movement* in creating space for collaborative innovation. In the next section, we present our findings.

4. A liminal threshold for collaborative innovation

4.1. Prologue – the DEB initiative

Working in a national public organisation, I-1 actively collaborated with multiple separate working groups in the DE field for several years. I-1 contemplated how to bring people together around the same need and alleviate the confusion of *‘having lots of inputs from many directions causing uncertainty of not knowing how the things were connected and where to start’*. After the events in the spring 2020, I-1 was inspired to experiment with a virtual space for cross-sectoral collaboration to enable a system-level understanding of the national DE infrastructure and to create future opportunities. In practice, this meant inviting people across sectors of society, that is businesses, NGOs, and universities, to meet online using a sort of snowball mechanism.

The original idea of this national initiative came from I-1 and was backed by I-2, who was known as a central and passionate expert in the fields of digitalisation and DE in the country. With I-2, I-1 began to brainstorm ways to construct a shared understanding of the activities in ongoing projects and plans across sectors. Both I-1 and I-2 believed that such a shared understanding would enable not only the development and efficiency of single projects, but also a more coordinated DE for the country in general. On October 8, 2020, I-2 and I-1 met to craft a baseline paper in which they drafted the objective and mission of the DEB to maintain a general view of what is going on in the DE of the country. They saw that a shared understanding of projects and data architectures with new ways of acting outwards from silos with open communication, combining projects, establishing thematic working groups, and maintaining agreed-upon principles were topical issues to discuss. After drafting their baseline paper, I-1 invited 11 key individuals

from different sectors working with the DE to a kick-off meeting to discuss whether there was a need for a collaborative space for the DE actors in the country and to hear more suggestions for the purpose of that space. To I-1's surprise, all those invited immediately accepted the e-mail invitation and engaged in planning with I-1 and I-2. The 11 persons who attended the first meeting on October 20 became the initial core group to further the DEB initiative.

4.2. Informants' parallel narratives on the purpose of DEB

The general purpose of the DEB initiative was rooted in the need to take down sectoral barriers and create a competitive advantage through the DE, with knowledge and coordination of activities in the field. As the core group shared a vision of advancing Finland's expertise and position as a digital forerunner at the EU level, understanding and interacting beyond sectoral boundaries was an essential asset. The central benefits of the DEB in the long term were seen in the possibilities of building ecosystems around data infrastructure with the necessary key actors and investments and in creating new businesses. Large investments had already been made in data infrastructure, and returns were now expected. In summary, the core group aimed to develop Finland's competitiveness in leveraging data, impacting regulation, and gaining competitiveness in the EU (and globally).

In the interviewees' descriptions of what the DEB initiative was for, we sensed their dissatisfaction with the current state of things. There was a need *‘to unlearn the old and change the culture to genuinely build things together’* (I-5). According to I-3, *‘things [were] done on small islands’*, while having no vision or structure to lead the advancement of digitalisation and DE. To this end, I-3 experienced quite a gap in how the DE was understood and acted upon in companies and at the policy level: *‘This wakes up people at the strategic level; this kind of critical mass of people has moved towards each other to discuss’*. In addition, for I-4, sharing information about the new and ongoing initiatives, knowing what and why things are done and crystallising the congruent understanding of what can be communicated in the EU were the two most important things in the core mission and purpose of the DEB.

Due to the fast pace of the industry sector, I-7 saw the DEB as an opportunity to enable large-scale

collaboration in the country, which was rather unique compared with other EU countries. I-7 pointed out the advantages of the small size of the country and agility in sharing information and creating a shared understanding. Despite not having a clear vision or structure for developing the DE, the smallness and openness of the country itself were seen to serve as a good starting point for a competitive advantage: *'It is questionable if this could be done in larger countries'* (I-9).

In I-5's words, DE was a multidisciplinary new phenomenon, and there was an enormous need for knowledge to enhance the understanding of it. For most of the core group members, the DEB represented an informal forum that allowed free knowledge flow, enabling a multidisciplinary perspective within the DE field. At its best, companies would also practically benefit from collaboration in national and European projects, while also being able to bring their innovative solutions to the European market. The background of this was the importance of thinking about the different levels of being active and influencing EU data strategies and programmes. For example, a collective understanding of how to administer data in a fair and transparent way would be a step towards more democratic platforms and a new competitive advantage for companies. As stated by I-10, *'I think that in this continuum of administration of these social systems, the next step is these more democratic platforms. [...] as the society develops, or the world develops, in many places, they turn to more democratic administrative entities'*.

4.3. The three dimensions of liminality

The interviewed individuals were active participants enabling us to see their subjective frames – them making sense of what the DEB was about. By first considering the individual interview accounts separate from each other and then next to each other again, we observed that by being in the same initiative with at least a partially shared vision, their interview accounts converged in various places. However, the research participants' expressions of the function of the initiative seemed to diverge and create tension among the organisers. Our further interpretation of the interviews illustrates how their accounts of the DEB initiative can be understood as manifestations of a *liminal* threshold for collaborative innovation. Figure 1 illustrates our findings with three dimensions of liminal space: confusion–clarity, isolation–communal and stagnation–movement.

Figure 1. A liminal threshold for collaborative innovation. [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

4.3.1. Confusion–clarity

Confusion, caused by many inputs and not knowing how to proceed without a clear view of the whole situation of the DE, gave the first clue towards articulating the DEB initiative as a liminal threshold for creating space for collaborative innovation. The participants' reflections on the overall ambiguous context of the DE turned our attention to the expressions of both confusion and uncertainty and the determination to overcome that ambiguous state they were in with the help of the DEB initiative.

Working closely at the interface between the public sector and decision-makers, the complex situation made I-3 ask himself, *'How could I be of service, and what should I be doing?'* I-3 tried to understand the developments in the DE for several years, but stated, *'Yet I have this feeling every day that, okay, I do not understand after all'*. There were expressions of worry, even guilt, because of not understanding what should be done next in the DE. Something should be done, but it is not clear what are the interconnections and what should be done first, and what are the roles of different actors: *'No one knows what has been done earlier or how the things are connected, so how is it possible to head towards the next phase when there is so much uncertainty?'* (I-1).

The confusion–clarity dimension highlights the unstructured and ambiguous state in which they find themselves and how the interaction at the DEB could help in resolving that not-yet-knowing state. The interviews illustrate how the underlying meaning of the initiative they took part in was to find a common direction and navigate the DE field together.

According to I-6, the challenging task of forming an image of what was going on created a real threat to people to keep working in their silos and be unable to take advantage of the synergies from collaboration. The DEB initiative was a concrete attempt to alleviate that confusion in the data economy field and the threat of staying isolated.

4.3.2. Isolation–communal

Across the interviews, the DEB was emphasised as an initiative to bring people and their different perspectives and resources (i.e. knowledge, expertise, funds) towards a common purpose; part of it was to ‘*updat[e] the shared DEB view together and connec[t] people for networking*’ (I-6). Searching for and finding each other in the complexities and uncertainties of the DE in real-time space and sharing the challenges and opportunities it was posing to them shows a degree of communal spirit where social conditions and roles can temporarily disappear or where diversity is valued.

Coming from the banking industry, I-9 had their own perspective on the purpose of a ‘*shared DEB view*’ of the data economy. For I-9, having the DEB was about trying to have both governmental and private sector actors in the same forum, which, in and of itself, is quite unusual. I-9 also emphasised that connecting competitors was unusual but possible because they understood that after collaborating, they could return to their normal competitive business positions with a more effective stance.

I-4, who had already taken part in the DE initiatives because of their work roles, expressed the need for multiple yet critical viewpoints. I-4 called for open discussion, debates, and raising critical tones, that is, not only ‘*smiling talk*’, to challenge the development of the DE for the better. Like I-4, I-5 described the DEB initiative as an effort to build a genuine conversation between different people, despite their rank or role: ‘*A larger objective, I see, is that we are building an ecosystem here, an ecosystem of people working around the DE. Connecting organisations and companies, but also individual people and civil servants. We are can build a genuine conversation between the public, the private, and researchers*’ (I-5).

From their accounts, we identified an isolation–community dimension of the data economy that highlights the social and connecting purpose of the DEB initiative. This isolation–communal dimension underlines the shifting position of the others in the ambiguous context of DE and being from another silo to being what we could call *communitas* (Turner, 1969) in navigating a liminal experience together and having support from each other. Due

to experiencing the liminality of the data economy together, they become equals at the threshold – the DEB initiative.

4.3.3. Stagnation–movement

The DEB initiative manifests a threshold for a national-level *transition* and movement from isolated and unstructured to a legitimate and communal way of working together for a common vision of the DE.

The members of the core group emphasised the collective power in the DEB initiative; for example, I-10 saw the need to attract a large group for legitimacy. I-10 also called for transcending DEB from being only a showroom of different perspectives towards a legitimate entity giving public statements.

Coming to the same collaborative space from different directions would also potentially raise critical discussions of what the DE means and what the DEB should be – and, eventually, what kind of actions should be taken, by whom, and when. At this stage, there was no clear talk or timeline of how to share a responsibility to start solving identified problems in the DE and to coordinate further actions (I-11) or whose task it was to build and maintain a living map of all projects or an Insight Bank in the country, as suggested by I-2.

And perhaps it crystallises to one bigger single fact that we do not have the ownership of the whole digitalisation scene, no one is ready to make big investments from their own budget for this common digitalisation because it is nobody’s responsibility at the moment directly. (I-11)

This third dimension highlights both the different kinds of movements towards *actions* the core group members see as meaningful in the collective aim towards a common vision and goal in the DEB initiative.

Framed as a threshold for collaborative innovation, the DEB initiative characterises a liminal space that emerges when people meet to share temporary spaces outside their formal organisations and any existing structures and when individuals experience a state of ambiguity and uncertainty in relation to the initiative, themselves, each other, and the surrounding context. Not only was it a confusing mental state where people did not see the big picture and had to navigate towards it, but it was also a complex social realm where people needed to find each other and create movement collectively to learn and take action, instead of working in isolation.

5. Discussion and conclusions

By adopting liminality as a lens, our study provides a nuanced understanding of creating spaces for collaborative innovation. Particularly by elaborating on participants' sense-making of initiating a space, we further conceptualised the three dimensions of a *liminal space* (see Figure 1), which here means the transitional threshold that orients the participants towards collaborative innovation. These dimensions are intertwined within the threshold, allowing collective sensemaking. If considered part of a continuum of sensemaking of events and actions, such liminal thresholds that create space for collaborative innovation are continuous and conjunctive (Cloutier and Langley, 2020), moving and transitioning participants towards future spaces.

5.1. Theoretical contributions

Our contribution to the literature on *collaborative innovation and spaces* is twofold. First, we propose a three-dimensional conceptualisation of a liminal space as a threshold for collaborative innovation. In past research, spaces have been related to physical spaces (e.g., open labs and maker spaces), whereas in spaces seen as being in-between organisations (Ollila and Yström, 2020), or otherwise liminal (see e.g. Caccamo, 2020) in nature, actors' experiences related to these spaces are as being 'not here, nor there', 'being nowhere', or as specific zones of 'third places' (Oldenburg, 1989) on neutral territory. Our study revealed this liminal in-betweenness as a necessary state in how individuals *mentally enter and inhabit a threshold* for creating space for collaborative innovation with different meanings to the process – a challenging but simultaneously important state of becoming that makes an ambiguous space into a meaningful place (Tuan, 1977; Cresswell, 2014). It creates an important threshold, or corridor, comprising the tensions and different perspectives of actors who enter the space, thus creating an opportunity for sensemaking, a shared view, and learning. The original notion of liminality also emphasises the communal experience of the limen, or *communitas*, meaning the potential importance of relationships between people during the shared experience of liminality (Turner, 1969; Küpers, 2011). In the end, liminal spaces can produce alternative social forms, norms, value systems, and activities (Söderlund and Borg, 2018) that have become meaningful for the experiencers of (creating) that space.

The second contribution of this study stems from our methodological approach and from considering a

microfoundation perspective on the phenomenon of collaborative innovation (considered by, e.g. Yström and Agogué, 2020). Past research on the emergence of open and collaborative innovation has focused more on the organisational and interorganisational levels of analysis (Lowik et al., 2017; Mazzucchelli et al., 2019). In particular, we add to the field by studying the individuals' sensemaking narratives (e.g. Weick et al., 2005; Brown et al., 2008) of the process of initiating space for collaborative innovation. By bringing in the micro-foundation perspective and narrative approach, we focus on individuals' perceptions and experiences and thus provide a novel way of seeing and understanding what the emergence of collaborative innovation entails. Particularly, our study highlights the importance of providing the necessary space (and time) for contemplating diverse views, perspectives, and ideas over the how-tos of initiating collaborative innovation, while anchoring to an overarching common vision and purpose (cf. Mazzucato, 2021).

5.2. Practical implications

Conceptualising the threshold for collaborative innovation through the three dimensions of liminal space enhances practitioners' understanding of the tensions related to the very early phase of collaborative innovation. This challenging phase requires patience so that diverse parties are willing and able to sustain their engagement and provide an opportunity for collaborative innovation to emerge. In contrast to the need for control and execution by traditional management, managers should maintain a pace that allows expressions of diverse, ambiguous, and confronting issues and enables collective learning and sensemaking to subsequently develop common ground (cf. Nonaka and Yamaguchi, 2022). While there may be 'negative psychological consequences of extended liminality' (Beech, 2011, p. 287) stemming from feelings of ambiguity and uncertainty, managers should consider the positive impacts of in-betweenness when entering collaboration. The challenges of liminality can be eased by anchoring the participants to a common purpose and/or vision. Hence, investing time and effort in collectively defining this purpose/vision becomes central.

5.3. Limitations and future research

Like any exploratory qualitative research, this study has some inherent limitations related to context specificity and generalisability, be it was conducted in Finland, a small, non-hierarchical, highly digitised country. Our findings might not be applicable to more

hierarchical and less digitised contexts. Nevertheless, our findings can apply to contexts and conditions in which individuals work in ambiguous, in-between positions or roles, such as those engaged in inter-organisational networks and projects (Tempest and Starkey, 2004; Ellis and Ybema, 2010). Having unusual access to the very initiation is a strength of our study. However, due to this timing, our interviews might reflect relatively more participants' positive expectations than encountered challenges.

A longitudinal micro-level process study would provide a more nuanced understanding of the nature of both sensemaking, as well as the emergence of collaborative innovation (Garud et al., 2013), and further investigation of individuals' potential to initiate space for collaborative innovation and to sustain innovation processes. Although a systematic analysis of the roles of individuals was beyond the scope of this paper, we call for research to explore the different roles that actors play (cf. Nyström et al., 2014; Ollila and Yström, 2017) in the collaborative innovation space.

Future research on the tensions and temporality in liminal spaces could examine practitioners' mental models and leadership practices to better understand the relational mechanisms and patterns in the emergence of ecosystems, what practices there are, and how they are used to allow diversity in perspectives, rhythms of activity and goals and to help sustain participants' motivation to engage in the process.

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Ethics statement

All participants gave recorded informed consent to participate in the study.

Data availability statement

The data that support the findings of this study are available on request from the corresponding author. The data are not publicly available due to privacy or ethical restrictions.

References

Adner, R. (2012) *The Wide Lens: A New Strategy for Innovation*. London: Penguin UK.

- Arena, M., Cross, R., Sims, J., and Uhl-Bien, M. (2017) How to catalyse innovation in your organization. *MIT Sloan Management Review*, **58**, 4, 38–48.
- Attour, A. and Barbaroux, P. (2016) Architectural knowledge and the birth of a platform ecosystem: a case study. *Journal of Innovation Economics Management*, **19**, 1, 11–30.
- Baldwin, C. and Von Hippel, E. (2011) Modeling a paradigm shift: from producer innovation to user and open collaborative innovation. *Organization Science*, **22**, 6, 1399–1417.
- Bartel, C.A. and Garud, R. (2009) The role of narratives in sustaining organizational innovation. *Organization Science*, **20**, 1, 107–117.
- Beckman, S.L. and Barry, M. (2007) Innovation as a learning process: embedding design thinking. *California Management Review*, **50**, 25–56.
- Beech, N. (2011) Liminality and the practices of identity reconstruction. *Human Relations*, **64**, 2, 285–302.
- Bessant, J. (2020) Creating the creative open lab. In: Fritzsche, A., Jonas, J., Roth, A., and Möslin, K.M. (eds), *Innovating in the Open Lab. The New Potential for Interactive Value Creation Across Organizational Boundaries*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg. pp. 191–202.
- Bogers, M., Zobel, A.-K., Afuah, A., Almirall, E., Brunswicker, S., Dahlander, L., Frederiksen, L., Gawer, A., Gruber, M., Haefliger, S., Hagedoorn, J., Hilgers, D., Laursen, K., Magnusson, M.G., Majchrzak, A., McCarthy, I.P., Moeslein, K.M., Nambisan, S., Piller, F.T., Radziwon, A., Rossi-Lamastra, C., Sims, J., and Ter Wal, A.L.J. (2017) The open innovation research landscape: established perspectives and emerging themes across different levels of analysis. *Industry and Innovation*, **24**, 1, 8–40.
- Boje, D.M. (2001) *Narrative Methods for Organizational & Communication Research*. London: Sage.
- Brown, J.S. and Duguid, P. (1991) Organizational learning and communities-of-practice: toward a unified view of working, learning, and innovation. *Organization Science*, **2**, 40–57.
- Brown, A.D., Stacey, P., and Nandhakumar, J. (2008) Making sense of sensemaking narratives. *Human Relations*, **61**, 8, 1035–1062.
- Bruner, J. (1991) The narrative construction of reality. *Critical Inquiry*, **18**, 1, 1–21.
- Caccamo, M. (2020) Leveraging innovation spaces to foster collaborative innovation. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, **29**, 1, 178–191.
- Capdevila, I. (2017) A typology of localized spaces of collaborative innovation. In: van Ham, M., Reuschke, D., Kleinhans, R., Syrett, S., and Mason, C. (eds), *Entrepreneurial Neighbourhoods – Towards an Understanding of the Economies of Neighbourhoods and Communities*. Cheltenham: Edward Elgar Publishers. pp. 80–97.
- Chesbrough, H.W. (2003) *Open Innovation: The New Imperative for Creating and Profiting from Technology*. Boston, MA: Harvard Business Press.
- Chesbrough, H. (2020) To recover faster from Covid-19, open up: managerial implications from an

- open innovation perspective. *Industrial Marketing Management*, **88**, 410–413.
- Cloutier, C. and Langley, A. (2020) What makes a process theoretical contribution? *Organization Theory*, **1**, 1–32.
- Connelly, F.M. and Clandinin, D.J. (1990) Stories of experience and narrative inquiry. *Educational Researcher*, **19**, 5, 2–14.
- Cresswell, T. (2014) *Place: An Introduction*. Chichester: John Wiley & Sons.
- Czarniawska, B. and Mazza, C. (2003) Consulting as a liminal space. *Human Relations*, **56**, 3, 267–290.
- Dattée, B., Alexy, O., and Autio, E. (2018) Maneuvering in poor visibility: how firms play the ecosystem game when uncertainty is high. *Academy of Management Journal*, **61**, 2, 466–498.
- Dhanaraj, C. and Parkhe, A. (2006) Orchestrating innovation networks. *Academy of Management Review*, **31**, 3, 659–669.
- Di Fiore, A. and Vetter, J. (2016) Why B2B companies struggle with collaborative innovation. *Harvard Business Review*. Accessed September 22, 2022. <https://hbr.org/2016/03/why-b2b-companies-struggle-with-collaborative-innovation>.
- Doz, Y.L., Olk, P.M., and Ring, P.S. (2000) Formation processes of R&D consortia: which path to take? Where does it lead? *Strategic Management Journal*, **21**, 3, 239–266.
- Eisenhardt, K.M. and Graebner, M. (2007) Theory building from cases: opportunities and challenges. *Academy of Management Journal*, **50**, 25–35.
- Ellis, N. and Ybema, S. (2010) Marketing identities: shifting circles of identification in inter-organizational relationships. *Organization Studies*, **31**, 3, 279–305.
- Enkel, E., Bogers, M., and Chesbrough, H. (2020) Exploring open innovation in the digital age: a maturity model and future research directions. *R&D Management*, **50**, 1, 161–168.
- Enkel, E., Gassmann, O., and Chesbrough, H. (2009) Open R&D and open innovation: exploring the phenomenon. *R&D Management*, **39**, 4, 311–316.
- Esin, C. (2011) Narrative analysis approaches. In: Frost, N. (ed.), *Qualitative Research Methods in Psychology. Combining Core Approaches*. Maidenhead, Berkshire: Open University Press, McGraw-Hill Education. pp. 92–118.
- European Commission, Directorate-General for Communications Networks, Content and Technology. (2017) *Building a European Data Economy*. Accessed September 22, 2022 <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=COM%3A2017%3A9%3AFIN#footnote2>
- Fachin, F.F. and Langley, A. (2018) Researching organizational concepts processually: the case of identity. In: Cassell, C., Cunliffe, A., and Grandy, G. (eds), *SAGE Handbook of Qualitative Business and Management Research Methods*. London: Sage. pp. 308–327.
- Ferraro, F., Etzion, D., and Gehman, J. (2015) Tackling grand challenges pragmatically: robust action revisited. *Organization Studies*, **36**, 3, 363–390.
- Garsten, C. (1999) Betwixt and between: temporary employees as liminal subjects in flexible organizations. *Organization studies*, **20**, 4, 601–617.
- Garud, R., Tuertscher, P., and Van de Ven, A.H. (2013) Perspectives on innovation processes. *Academy of Management Annals*, **7**, 1, 775–819.
- van Gennep, A. (1909) *Les rites de passage. Étude systématique des rites*. Paris: Picard.
- Gioia, D.A. and Chittipeddi, K. (1991) Sensemaking and sensegiving in strategic change initiation. *Strategic Management Journal*, **12**, 6, 433–448.
- Greer, C.R. and Lei, D. (2012) Collaborative innovation with customers: a review of the literature and suggestions for future research. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, **14**, 1, 63–84.
- Heil, S. and Bornemann, T. (2018) Creating shareholder value via collaborative innovation: the role of industry and resource alignment in knowledge exploration. *R&D Management*, **48**, 4, 394–409.
- von Hippel, E. (2005) *Democratizing Innovation*. Cambridge, MA: MIT Press.
- Ibarra, H. and Obodaru, O. (2016) Betwixt and between identities: liminal experience in contemporary careers. *Research in Organizational Behavior*, **36**, 47–64.
- Ketchen, D.J., Jr., Ireland, R.D., and Snow, C.C. (2007) Strategic entrepreneurship, collaborative innovation, and wealth creation. *Strategic Entrepreneurship Journal*, **1**, 3–4, 371–385.
- Küpers, W. (2011) Dancing on the limen~~~embodied and creative inter-places as thresholds of be(com)ing: phenomenological perspectives on liminality and transitional spaces in organization and leadership. *Tamara: Journal for Critical Organization Inquiry*, **9**, 3–4, 45–59.
- Lieblich, A., Tuval-Mashiach, R., and Zilber, T. (1998) *Narrative Research: Reading, Analysis, and Interpretation*, Vol. **47**. London: Sage.
- Lowik, S., Kraaijenbrink, J., and Groen, A.J. (2017) Antecedents and effects of individual absorptive capacity: a micro-foundational perspective on open innovation. *Journal of Knowledge Management*, **21**, 6, 1319–1341.
- Maclean, M., Harvey, C., and Chia, R. (2012) Sensemaking, storytelling and the legitimization of elite business careers. *Human Relations*, **65**, 1, 17–40.
- Mazzucato, M. (2021) *Mission Economy: A Moonshot Guide to Changing Capitalism*. London: Penguin Random House.
- Mazzucchelli, A., Chierici, R., Abbate, T., and Fontana, S. (2019) Exploring the microfoundations of innovation capabilities. evidence from a cross-border R&D partnership. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, **146**, 242–252.
- Miles, R.E., Miles, G., and Snow, C.C. (2005) *Collaborative Entrepreneurship: How Communities of Networked Firms Use Continuous Innovation to Create Economic Wealth*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press.
- Miles, R.E., Snow, C.C., and Miles, G. (2000) TheFuture.org. *Long Range Planning*, **33**, 300–321.
- Ministry of Transport and Communications. (2021) *Study: Finland Active in Developing Data Economy*. Accessed

- September 22, 2022 <https://www.lvm.fi/-/study-finland-active-in-developing-data-economy-1574418>
- Muhr, S.L., De Cock, C., Twardowska, M., and Volkman, C. (2019) Constructing an entrepreneurial life: liminality and emotional reflexivity in identity work. *Entrepreneurship and Regional Development*, **31**, 7–8, 567–582.
- Nonaka, I. and Yamaguchi, I. (2022) *Management by Eidetic Intuition: A Dynamic Management Theory Predicated on the “Philosophy of Empathy”*. Singapore: Springer Nature.
- Nyström, A.G., Leminen, S., Westerlund, M., and Kortelainen, M. (2014) Actor roles and role patterns influencing innovation in living labs. *Industrial Marketing Management*, **43**, 3, 483–495.
- Oldenburg, R. (1989) *The Great Good Place: Cafés, Coffee Shops, Community Centers, Beauty Parlors, General Stores, Bars, Hangouts, and How They Get You Through the Day*. New York: Paragon House Publishers.
- Ollila, S. and Yström, A. (2017) An investigation into the roles of open innovation collaboration managers. *R&D Management*, **47**, 2, 236–252.
- Ollila, S. and Yström, A. (2020) Open laboratories as “in-between spaces”. In: Fritzsche, A., Jonas, J., Roth, A., and Möslein, K.M. (eds), *Innovating in the Open Lab. The New Potential for Interactive Value Creation Across Organizational Boundaries*. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter Oldenbourg. pp. 203–212.
- Ollila, S. and Yström, A. (2021) Designing spaces for collaborative innovation: the role of organizational politics. *Conference Proceedings, the ISPIM Innovation Conference – Innovating Our Common Future*, Berlin, Germany, 20–23 June 2021. pp. 1–20.
- Peschl, M.F. and Fundneider, T. (2008) Emergent innovation and sustainable knowledge co-creation. A socio-epistemological approach to “innovation from within”. In: Lytras, M.D., Carroll, J.M., Damiani, E., Tennyson, R.D., Avison, D., Vossen, G., and De Pablos, P.O. (eds), *The Open Knowledge Society. A Computer Science and Information Systems Manifesto*. WSKS 2008. Communications in Computer and Information Science, Vol. **19**. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer. pp. 101–108.
- Peschl, M.F. and Fundneider, T. (2014) Why space matters for collaborative innovation networks: on designing enabling spaces for collaborative knowledge creation. *International Journal of Organizational Design and Engineering*, **3**, 3–4, 358–391.
- Riessman, C.K. (1993) *Narrative Analysis*, Vol. **30**. Newbury Park, CA: Sage.
- Ring, P.S. and Van de Ven, A.H. (1994) Developmental processes of cooperative interorganizational relationships. *Academy of Management Review*, **19**, 1, 90–118.
- Ryan, A. (2019) Guiding and enabling liminal experiences between business and arts organizations operating in a sponsorship relationship. *Human Relations*, **72**, 2, 344–369.
- Schmidhuber, L., Piller, F., Bogers, M., and Hilgers, D. (2019) Citizen participation in public administration: investigating open government for social innovation. *R&D Management*, **49**, 3, 343–355.
- Shortt, H. (2015) Liminality, space and the importance of ‘transitory dwelling places’ at work. *Human Relations*, **68**, 4, 633–658.
- Shotter, J. (2006) Understanding process from within: an argument for ‘withness’-thinking. *Organization Studies*, **27**, 4, 585–604.
- de Silva, M., Lavelle, O., Schmidt, N., and Paunov, C. (2022) *Co-creation During COVID-19: 30 Comparative International Case Studies* (No. 135). Paris: OECD Publishing.
- de Silva, M., Schmidt, N., Paunov, C., and Lavelle, O. (2022) *How Did COVID-19 Shape Co-Creation? Insights and Policy Lessons from International Initiatives* (No. 134). Paris: OECD Publishing.
- Sinkovics, R.R. and Alfoldi, E.A. (2012) Progressive focusing and trustworthiness in qualitative research – the enabling role of computer-assisted qualitative data analysis software (CAQDAS). *Management International Review*, **52**, 817–845.
- Sitra. (2022) *A Roadmap for a Fair Data Economy*. Accessed September 22, 2022 <https://www.sitra.fi/en/topics/roadmap-for-the-data-economy/>
- Söderlund, J. and Borg, E. (2018) Liminality in management and organization studies: process, position and place. *International Journal of Management Reviews*, **20**, 4, 880–902.
- Sørensen, E. and Torfing, J. (2012) Introduction: collaborative innovation in the public sector. *The Innovation Journal*, **17**, 1, 1–14.
- Stake, R.E. (2008) Qualitative case studies. In: Denzin, N.K. and Lincoln, Y.S. (eds), *Strategies of Qualitative Inquiry*. Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage. pp. 119–149.
- Stenner, P. (2017) *Liminality and Experience: A Transdisciplinary Approach to the Psychosocial*. Studies in the psychosocial (STIP). London: Palgrave Macmillan.
- Stephenson, K.A., Kuismäki, A., Putnam, L.L., and Sivunen, A. (2020) Process studies of organizational space. *Academy of Management Annals*, **14**, 2, 797–827.
- Stigliani, I. and Ravasi, D. (2012) Organizing thoughts and connecting brains: material practices and the transition from individual to group-level prospective sensemaking. *Academy of Management Journal*, **55**, 5, 1232–1259.
- Swink, M. (2006) Building collaborative innovation capability. *Research-Technology Management*, **49**, 2, 37–47.
- Tagliaventi, M.R. (2019) *Liminality in Organization Studies: Theory and Method*. New York: Routledge.
- Tempest, S. and Starkey, K. (2004) The effects of liminality on individual and organizational learning. *Organization Studies*, **25**, 4, 507–527.
- Tsoukas, H. (2009) A dialogical approach to the creation of new knowledge in organizations. *Organization Science*, **20**, 6, 941–957.
- Tuan, Y. (1977) *Space and Place: The Perspective of Experience*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota.
- Turner, V.W. (1969) *The Ritual Process: Structure and Anti-Structure*. London: Routledge and Kegan Paul.

- Uhl-Bien, M. (2021) Complexity and COVID-19: leadership and followership in a complex world. *Journal of Management Studies*, **58**, 5, 1400–1404.
- Välikangas, L. and Jarvenpaa, S.L. (2021) How collaborative networks fail, with the implications for participants learning. In: Todt, G., Backmann, J., and Weiss, M. (eds), *Work Life After Failure? How Employees Bounce Back, Learn, and Recover from Work-Related Setbacks*. Bingley: Emerald Publishing Limited. pp. 173–190.
- Viki, T. (2016) Five reasons your boss was right to shut down your innovation lab. *Forbes*. Accessed September 22, 2022. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/tendayiviki/2016/09/04/five-reasons-your-boss-was-right-to-close-your-innovation-lab/?sh=2721b8f11c45>.
- Weick, K.E., Sutcliffe, K.M., and Obstfeld, D. (2005) Organizing and the process of sensemaking. *Organization Science*, **16**, 4, 409–421.
- Wenger, E. (1998) *Communities of Practice: Learning, Meaning, and Identity*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Yström, A. and Agogué, M. (2020) Exploring practices in collaborative innovation: unpacking dynamics, relations, and enactment in in-between spaces. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, **29**, 1, 141–145.

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APPENDIX A. NARRATIVE INTERVIEW GUIDE

This narrative interview guide was used to discuss the ongoing activities (Maclean et al., 2012) provided by the informants, giving them the central role and freedom to talk at their own pace about their subjective experiences of being involved in the launching of the initiative.

Ongoing activities:

For example, 'How did it all start? What is happening now? What are you doing in practice?'

About the participants' own interests in taking part in the activities:

For example, 'What is inspiring here? What makes it meaningful to you?'

How would they see the future of the initiative in their own terms:

For example, 'How do you see things should and could unfold? How would the Boardroom be at its best?'

APPENDIX B. DATA COLLECTION

	Main data	
Data items	11 interviews (each ≈ 30 min).	Official reports of digitalisation and data economy development, blog post(s), presentations, workshop materials, meeting memos, and emails. Analysis of interviews was enhanced by familiarisation with the contextual underpinnings and societal discourse of data economy development and digitalisation.
Description of the data	Transcribed interviews with experts from companies, university, and public sector who were involved during the process, shared their knowledge, expertise or provided further information and opportunities. 11 handwritten interview memos.	Pdf, ppt, word format files and posts. Discussions on emails, shared materials, memos.
Timing	23.11.2020–08.01.2021	

APPENDIX C. TABLE OF CONTENTS IN THE DESCRIPTIVE SUMMARY FOR THE CORE GROUP ON DECEMBER 18, 2020

1. Starting point for action
 - the need for organised collaborative action
 - anticipated benefits
2. Expectations for outcomes and goals for the collaborative action
 - common understanding
 - concrete outcomes, influencing at the EU level, ecosystem activity
3. The concept-in-the-making (networking activities)
 - common understanding of themes and focus
 - self-critics
 - trust, ethics, and rules for action
 - different views of organising activities